

HIGH THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CARBON NANOTUBE SHEET/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have high electrical and thermal conductivity and mechanical strength [1]. The theoretical thermal conductivity of a single-walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT) is predicted to reach over 6600 W/mK [2]. Experimental measurements of a multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) and SWCNT exhibit thermal conductivities over 3000 W/mK [3] and 3500 W/mK [4], respectively. The issue is how to transfer these properties into bulk materials. CNT sheets (or buckypapers) consisting of entangled networks of CNTs show thermal conductivity of 20 - 30 W/mK at room temperature in experiments conducted using a comparative method [5]. Thermal conductivity of buckypaper/epoxy composite reduced the thermal conductivity to 5 W/mK at room temperature due to epoxy in between carbon nanotubes [5].

Aligning the nanotubes in the CNT sheets is an effective approach to improve the thermal conductivity as well as their electrical and mechanical properties. For this purpose, external magnetic fields, electric fields and mechanical stretching have been shown to improve CNT alignment in CNT sheets [5-7] or composites [8].

For nanotube-polymer composites, adding either SWCNTs or MWCNTs increase the thermal conductivity [9] compared to pristine polymers. Higher loading of carbon nanotubes results in higher thermal conductivity, but its thermal conductivity value is far below its theoretical predictions based on the simple rule of mixture due to large interface scattering and contact resistances [10]. This study attempted to use long-MWCNTs and better alignment to improve the thermal conductivity of CNT sheet/epoxy composites.

2 Experimental

Raw materials for long-MWCNT I and short-MWCNTs were purchased from Cnano (CA, USA). Long-MWCNT sheets were purchased from Nanocomp (NH, USA) and long-MWCNT II was prepared after sonication of the sheets, as shown in Figure 1. EPON862 with epicure-W was used to make nanotube/epoxy composites. For the low concentration CNT composite fabrication, long-MWCNTs were mixed with epoxy based on the target weight percentage, sonicated in a cooling bath and cured in a hot press for 2 hrs at 177°C followed by 30 min at 90°C. The resultant composites had a CNT contents ranging from 2 wt. % to 10 wt. %.

To increase nanotube concentration, the CNT sheets were used with diluted epoxy and cured in a hot press [11]. The typical weight percentage of CNTs in the CNT sheet/epoxy composites was over 60 wt. %. A mechanical stretching approach was also used

Fig.1. SEM images of (a) long-MWCNT II in epoxy (6.38 wt.%), (b) short-MWCNT in epoxy (10 wt.%), (c) random MWCNT sheet and (d) aligned MWCNT sheet.

Fig.2. Room temperature thermal conductivity (κ_{RT}) of MWCNT/epoxy composite.

to improve the degree of alignment in the CNT sheet composites.

Figure 1 shows the field-emission scanning electron microscope images of (a) long-MWCNT in the epoxy composite (6.38 wt. %), (b) short-MWCNT in the epoxy composite (10 wt. %), (c) random long-MWCNT sheet, and (d) aligned long-MWCNT sheet after mechanical stretching in the tensile stage.

The in-plane thermal conductivity was measured by the physical property measurement system (PPMS, Quantum Design) with thermal transport option.

3 Data and Results

3.1 The effects of nanotube length

Figure 2 shows a summary of room temperature thermal conductivities for short- and long-MWCNT/epoxy composites as a function CNT concentration. The higher MWCNT loading in the epoxy provided higher thermal conductivity.

The long-MWCNT composites exhibited higher thermal conductivity than the short-MWCNT composites when the weight percentages were the same. At room temperature, 10 wt. % short-MWCNT/epoxy composites showed thermal conductivity of 0.35 W/mK, which was nearly twice of the thermal conductivity of epoxy resin itself, 0.2 W/mK. However, the long-MWCNT composites showed 0.9 W/mK (Cnano) and 2.6 W/mK (Nanocomp) even at lower concentrations of 2.0 wt. % and 6.38 wt. %, respectively. Both the longer CNTs and high concentration of CNTs improved the higher thermal conductivity.

Fig. 3. Temperature dependence of (a) 25% stretched and (b) 40% stretched long-MWCNT sheet/epoxy composite both parallel and perpendicular direction. Line is in the case of random MWCNT sheet/epoxy composite. Inset shows log-log plot in the mid-temperature range to show the quadratic temperature dependence.

By further increasing the nanotube weight percentage to 60 wt. % using random long-MWCNT sheets, higher thermal conductivity up to 55 W/mK was achieved in the composite, which is nearly three times higher than the reported value of buckypaper/epoxy composite [5].

3.2 The effects of nanotube alignment

Figure 3 shows the temperature dependence of thermal conductivity of 25% and 40% stretch-induced aligned long-MWCNT sheet/epoxy composites along the parallel and perpendicular directions. Based on polarized Raman spectroscopy, 25% stretch and 40% stretch ratio achieved

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Fig. 4. Anisotropy of thermal conductivity in 25% and 40% stretched MWCNT sheet/epoxy composite. Line is for the case of isotropic random sheet composite.

alignment degree of 0.5 and 0.8, respectively [6]. At room temperature, their thermal conductivity increased up to 80 W/mK (25%) and 103 W/mK (40%). The thermal conductivity of 40% stretched MWCNT sheet composites measurements doubled compared to random long-MWCNT sheet/epoxy composite. A higher degree of alignment in the CNT sheets improved thermal conductivity through the aligned direction at all temperature ranges. The line shows the temperature dependence of thermal conductivity of random CNT sheet/epoxy composite for comparison.

The inset of figure 3 shows the logarithmic plot of temperature dependence. Thermal conductivity showed nearly a quadratic temperature dependence ($\kappa \propto T^n$, $n=2.0\sim 2.2$) at temperatures below 120K. Thermal conductivity showed linear temperature dependence afterward and saturated at the high temperature range in both the parallel and perpendicular alignment directions. The temperature dependence and exponent were almost the same in both directions, which indicates that the thermal transport mechanism is the same. The exponent is due to the two-dimensional nature of phonon distribution [7, 12]. The saturation at high temperatures confirmed the reduced radiation from the surface and onset of the Umklapp process.

Thermal conductivity through the perpendicular direction was lower than the parallel direction and the anisotropy ($\kappa_{||}/\kappa_{\perp}$) was 2.2 and 4.9 at room temperature in 25% and 40% stretched BP/epoxy composites, respectively. Figure 4 shows the

temperature dependence of the anisotropy of thermal conductivity, which was almost the same over the entire temperature range. However, the anisotropy of thermal conductivity was lower than that of the electrical anisotropy [13].

4 Conclusions

The thermal conductivities of various MWCNT/epoxy composites at different concentrations were measured. The long-MWCNT composites showed a higher thermal conductivity than the short-MWCNTs. At room temperature, a higher concentration (60 wt. %) of long-MWCNT sheet/epoxy composites showed thermal conductivity ~ 55 W/mK, and the mechanical stretch-induced alignment improved it further to over 103 W/mK (40% stretched). Higher concentration and alignment of long-MWCNT resulted in less intertube contact barriers and higher thermal conductivity in the resultant composites. Temperature dependence of thermal conductivity followed a well-known phonon-scattering process.

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References

- [1] A. Jorio, G. Dresselhaus, M. S. Dresselhaus, *Carbon Nanotubes: Advanced Topics in the Synthesis, Structure, Properties and Applications*, Springer, 2008.
- [2] S. Berber, Y. K. Kwon and D. Tomaneck "Unusually high thermal conductivity of carbon nanotubes". *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 84, 4613, 2000.
- [3] P. Kim, L. Shi, A. Majumdar, P. L. McEuen "Thermal transport measurements of individual multiwalled nanotubes". *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 87, 215502, 2001.
- [4] E. Pop, D. Mann, Q. Wang, K. Goodson, H. Dai "Thermal conductance of an individual single-wall carbon nanotube above room temperature". *Nano Lett.* 6 (1), 96-100, 2006.
- [5] P. Gonnet, Z. Liang, E. S. Choi, R. S. Kadambala, C. Zhang, J. S. Brooks, B. Wang, L. Kramer "Thermal

conductivity of magnetically aligned carbon nanotube buckypapers and nanocomposites". *Curr. Appl. Phys.* 6, 119 (2006).

- [6] Q. Cheng, J. Bao, J. G. Park, Z. Liang, C. Zhang, B. Wang "High Mechanical Performance Composite Conductor: Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotube Sheet/Bismaleimide Nanocomposites". *Adv. Func. Mater.* 19, 3219 (2009).
- [7] J. Hone, M. C. Llaguno, N. M. Nemes, A. T. Johnson, J. E. Fischer, D. A. Walters, M. J. Casavant, J. Schmidt, R. E. Smalley "Electrical and thermal transport properties of magnetically aligned single wall carbon nanotube films". *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 77, 666 (2000).
- [8] E. S. Choi, J. S. Brooks, D. L. Eaton, M. S. Al-Haik, M. Y. Hussaini, H. Garmestani, D. Li, K. Dahmen "Enhancement of thermal and electrical properties of carbon nanotube polymer composites by magnetic field processing". *J. Appl. Phys.* 94, 6034 (2003).
- [9] M. J. Biercuk, M. C. Llaguno, M. Radosavljevic, J. K. Hyun, A. T. Johnson, J. E. Fischer "Carbon nanotube composites for thermal management". *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 80, 2767 (2002).
- [10] C. -W. Nan, G. Liu, Y. Lin, M. Li "Interface effect on thermal conductivity of carbon nanotube composites". *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 85, 3549 (2004).
- [11] Z. Wang, Z. Liang, B. Wang, C. Zhang and L. Kramer "Processing and property investigation of single-walled carbon nanotube (SWNT) buckypaper/epoxy resin matrix nanocomposites". *Composite Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 35, 1225 (2004).
- [12] J. Hone *Dekker Encyclopedia of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*, 603, Marcel Dekker: New York, 2004.
- [13] J. G. Park, Q. Cheng, J. Lu, J. Bao, Y. Tian, Z. Liang, C. Zhang and B. Wang "Effect of alignment and length on the thermal conductivity of MWCNT/epoxy composites". *submitted*.